

On the influence of structural and chemical properties on the elastic modulus of woven bone under healing

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Abstract: Woven bone, a heterogeneous and temporary tissue in bone regeneration, is remodeled by osteoblastic and osteoclastic activity and shaped by mechanical stress to restore healthy tissue properties. Characterizing this tissue at different length scales is crucial for developing micromechanical models to optimize mechanical parameters which control regeneration and prevent non-unions. This study examines the temporal evolution of the mechanical properties of bone distraction callus using nanoindentation, ash analysis, micro-CT for trabecular microarchitecture, and Raman spectroscopy for mineral quality. It also defines single- and two-parameter power laws based on experimental data to predict tissue and bulk mechanical properties. At the macro-scale, the tissue exhibited a considerable increase in the bone fraction controlled by the widening of trabeculae, which play a more significant role than their chemical composition in the apparent elastic modulus of the tissue. Raman mineral-to-matrix ratio rose to cortical bone levels during regeneration, but the local elastic modulus remained lower, likely due to trabecular microporosities. Raman parameters were demonstrated to provide more significant power laws correlations with the micro-scale elastic modulus than mineral content from ash analysis.

Keywords: Woven bone; nanoindentation; micro-CT; Raman spectroscopy; Composition; distraction osteogenesis; elastic modulus; power law

1. Introduction

During skeletal tissue differentiation processes such as distraction osteogenesis, fracture healing, adaptation to skeletal implants, bone development and regeneration, the structure and composition of the mineralized bone tissue (referred to as woven bone or immature bone) continually change due to growth and responses to the tissue environment, including physical, chemical, and mechanical factors [1–5]. The organic and inorganic matrices of woven bone are highly dynamic and undergo alterations in their structure and composition [6–9]. The inorganic phase is primarily composed of nonstoichiometric hydroxyapatite crystals. This mineral content is deposited in two phases: an initial phase in which 70% of the final mineral content is incorporated within a few weeks, followed by a second phase in which the mineral content increases over months and years [10]. The organic phase is predominantly composed of type I collagen, along with various biomacromolecules, including proteoglycans and non-collagenous proteins [11]. During the initial stages of healing, naïve collagen fibers are randomly oriented due to their rapid formation. As the maturation progresses, these fibers increase in density, reorient, and structurally mature [12]. This maturation is understood as the process in which the fibers are crosslinked and packaged to accommodate mineralization. These microstructure arrangements result in a time-dependent mechanical behavior of the tissue, with initial stiffness much lower than that of the matured cortical and trabecular bones.

The microstructure and composition of bone play crucial roles in its macroscopic structural and mechanical behavior. Their relationship has been extensively studied in cortical and trabecular bones [13–16]. It has been shown that the elastic modulus of the mature bones strongly depends

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on mineral content, while toughness correlates with the quality of the collagen matrix [17]. Correlations between the elastic modulus and the bone mineral density have been established to estimate mechanical properties from the image-based measurements of the bone mineral density at both the organ and tissue scales (see [18] for a complete review). At the organ level, the elastic modulus (E) is related to the apparent mineral density ρ (mineralized bone mass/bulk volume) through a power law relationship ($E \propto \rho^b$). For cortical bones, b ranges between 4 and 7.4 [13,19] and for trabecular bones, it is normally lower ($b = 1.27\text{--}2.57$ [20–22]), indicating lower apparent stiffness. One limitation of these models is that they do not distinguish the influence of bone volume fraction from ash fraction. Therefore, at the macro- level, these correlations are improved when porosity [13,19] or fabric orientation are included [23–25]. However, this relationship is weak at the tissue level, likely due to the effect of microstructural features at small length scales [18]. In the woven bone, García-Rodríguez et al. [26] showed that a 6th-degree polynomial equation best fits the elastic modulus versus the ash fraction, predicted by a multiscale computational homogenization model. In their *in silico* model, they assumed isotropic orientation of collagen fibrils and used the ash fraction reported by Martínez-Reina et al. [6]. A simple exponential regression equation based on the ash fraction α , $E = 12.88 \cdot \alpha^{2.75}$, was also provided with a significant correlation coefficient. To date, no previous work has proposed power laws based on experimental data to predict the apparent mechanical properties of woven bone at micro- or macro-scales considering the evolutionary structure of this tissue.

Various techniques have been developed to assess the bone inorganic matrix at macroscopic scale to measure bone mineral density or mineral content: computed tomography [14,27], micro-computed tomography, dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry [22,24], ashing the sample [6,19] or weighing it [13,20,23,25]. To account for local variations in mineral content, scanning small angle X-ray scattering and wide angle X-ray scattering have been used to measure mineral crystal length and thickness [10]. Quantitative backscattered electron microscopy is a validated method for determining spatially resolved calcium content [10], and Fourier Transform infrared microspectroscopy and Raman microspectroscopy have been widely used to study the inorganic chemical compositional changes of the bone [28–32], including mineralization, crystallinity, or carbonate substitution amongst others. Turunen et al. [8] used infrared and Raman microspectroscopy to study inorganic chemical compositional changes during bone ageing and concluded that Raman microspectroscopy is more sensitive for the inorganic matrix. Bone healing processes have also been monitored with Raman spectroscopy [33–35]. Ahmed et al. [33] studied early healing in calvarial defects, which heal spontaneously, with Raman Spectroscopy. They showed an increase in mineral/matrix and crystallinity ratios and a reduction in the carbonate/phosphate ratio after 14 days of healing. However, the long-term temporal evolution of the mechanical, chemical and morphological properties of woven bone during healing in critical-sized bone defects remains unknown. Beyond ash analysis, using Raman spectra or backscattered electron signals as reliable input data for building power laws to predict the mechanical properties of bone tissue has not been explored to date.

Methods for evaluating the mechanical properties of bone tissue are more standardized. Macroscopic mechanical properties of cortical and trabecular bones have been traditionally evaluated through different mechanical testing including tension, compression, torsion, three-point bending, or buckling [36–40]. Local mechanics of mature tissue has been also assessed with ultrasound microscopy [41–43], nanoindentation [14,44–47] or atomic force microscopy [48]. However, for woven bone and its evolutionary properties, studies have used both *in vivo* [1,49–52] and *ex vivo* approaches [12,53,54] to provide values of local and apparent stiffness at different time-points during healing. Typically, *in vivo* mechanical properties are indirectly measured through instrumentation of surgically implanted fixations [1,49–52]. For *ex vivo* techniques, nanoindentation tests have proven valid to account for nanoscale heterogeneity and examine bone quality at a lower scale [2,55–57]. For instance, Manjubala et al. [56] and Mora-Macías et al. [57] measured the nanoindentation modulus for woven bone during fracture healing and bone transport processes, respectively.

In silico models are valuable for the understanding the course of healing from a mechanobiological perspective. Many researchers have sought to establish relationships between the mechanical

properties of undifferentiated tissue and ultimate tissue phenotype formed in a wide variety of bone regeneration processes, such as fracture healing (see [58,59] for a review), distraction osteogenesis [60–62] or tissue engineering [63,64], amongst others. As a limitation, all these works develop phenomenologic rules based on empirical observations and input parameters that are not sufficiently validated with experimental data, leaving room for improvement in accuracy. In particular, most of these models assumed constant values for the elastic modulus and porosity of the woven bone, regardless of its mineralized state or degree of matrix organization, which is not explicitly modeled. A constant porosity value of 80% and an elastic modulus of 1000 MPa are typically assigned to the woven bone in most of these mechanobiological evolutive models [60,65,66].

The main aim of this study is to identify time-related changes at the macro- and micro-scales at the chemical, mechanical, and morphological properties of the woven bone during healing of a critical-size bone defect. There is a need for a better understanding of the woven bone micromechanics and the development of a reliable mechanical model of this tissue to improve the prediction of its stiffness. For this purpose, at the microscopic scale, micromechanical properties will be measured with nanoindentation; mineral and organic characteristics will be quantified through Raman spectroscopy; and structural features through micro-CT. At the macroscopic scale, ash and element analyses will be assessed together with a numerical model to reproduce the woven bone bulk mechanical behavior based on physical measurements. All these experimental data will be used to build power laws relating the elastic modulus with the structural and chemical properties of the woven bone for the first time.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Origin and preparation of the woven bone samples

The woven bone samples analyzed in the current study originate from previous *in vivo* distraction osteogenesis experiments conducted on the right-back metatarsi of six skeletally-mature female Merino sheep [1,67]. The animals followed a surgical intervention and a bone lengthening protocol approved by the Animal Ethics of the University of Córdoba (Reference 2021PI/21), in compliance with the European (2010/63/UE) and national (RD 1201/2005) regulations. During the surgery, an Ilizarov-type external fixator was implanted in the metatarsus, and a cross-sectional osteotomy was performed in an intermediate section of the diaphysis. Consequently, each metatarsus was divided into two initially unconnected bone fragments, with their alignment ensured by the fixator device. After a 15-day latency period during which the bone healing begins by way of a preliminary soft callus formation, the fragments were distracted at rate of 1 mm/day during 15 days, as shown in Figure 1A. The resulting 15-mm bone callus was then allowed to mineralize over time. The specimens were sacrificed at different time-points of the distraction and consolidation phases to analyze *ex vivo* different states of callus ossification: days 18, 29, 47, 64, 112 and 161 after surgery. While more details on the design of the external fixator was provided by Blázquez-Carmona et al. [68], the distraction protocol was further described by Blázquez-Carmona et al. [67]. After sacrifice, operated limbs were immediately stored at -80°C .

Two slices of each bone callus, each approximately 3 mm thick, were cut in the frontal plane to address potential differences in the lateral-medial direction, as indicated in Figure 1B. These cuts were performed using a Femi FM-785XL band saw (Femi, Castel Guelfo, Bologna, Italy) while the sample was freshly taken out of the freezer to maintain the integrity of both the surrounding soft tissues and the callus itself. The first slice was used for micro-CT, Raman Spectroscopy and nanoindentation analysis. For micro-CT, the sample was analyzed in the same condition as cut. However, the other techniques required embedding and subsequent surface polishing to achieve flat and parallel surfaces. For embedding, a 40-mm diameter cylindrical polypropylene mold (FixiForm, Struers, California, US) and a slow-curing epoxy resin (Epofix, Struers, California, US) were employed. This resin hardens at room temperature in 24 hours, thus avoiding alterations in the mechanical or chemical properties of the sample due to high curing temperatures. Following the guidelines provided by Mora-Macías et al. [57], the surfaces of the embedded samples were polished by means of carbide papers (P600 to P4000) and diamond slurry (from 3 to 0.25 μm), cleaning them ultrasonically with distilled water after each polishing step. The second slice was

used to analyze the chemical composition of each bone callus, for which the cortical fragments were excised. No additional preparation was needed for this second slice. All samples were stored in PBS-soaked gauze and plastic wrap at -80°C prior to each analysis. As a reference for the interpretation and discussion of the micro-CT results, trabecular and cortical samples from a non-operated ovine metatarsus were also cut and preserved as detailed above. Similarly, as a control for the chemical analysis, cortical fragments of each operated metatarsus were prepared.

Figure 1. (A) Scheme of the osteotomized metatarsus and the distraction protocol; (B) scheme of the frontal plane sliced and analyzed from each operated limb; (C) image of a bone callus sample being imaged in the tomography; (D) 3D reconstruction of one of the bone calluses and volume of interest structurally analyzed; (E) visualization of microscope image of a bone callus sample. An example of cortical and woven bone areas to be analyzed by Raman Spectroscopy and nanoindentation are indicated; (F) scheme of the embedded bone callus samples and the areas analyzed; (G) example of a raw Raman spectra of the bone and the embedding resin; (H) comparison of corrected Raman spectra between cortical and woven bones; (I) load function applied by the indenter during a nanoindentation measure; (J) comparison of the indentation curve between cortical and woven bones; (K) nanoindentation of a cortical bone area; (L) nanoindentation of a woven bone area.

2.2. Micro-computed tomography of the bone calluses

Micro-CT images were taken using a Cougar tomography® (Y.Cougar SMT, Yxlon, Hudson, Ohio, US) with the following settings: 4x optical magnification; exposure time of 9 s; voxel size of $3.72\ \mu\text{m}$; source setting of 50 kV and $90.02\ \mu\text{m}$; and a physical size of approximately $25 \times 25 \times 25\ \text{mm}$. Figure 1C shows an image of one of the samples in the micro-CT during imaging. The tomographies were processed using the image analysis platform Thermo Scientific Avizo Software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts, US). A median filter (3D interpretation, 6 neighborhood pixels, 3 iterations) was initially applied to reduce the contrast, soften the edges of the woven bone, and facilitate segmentation. A mixed automatic-manually interactive thresholding was performed, followed by a small noise spot removal with a maximum size of 100 px. The 3D structures were cropped into an inner cube covering the entire bone callus volume. An example of

a thresholded sample and the cropped bone callus volume of interest is provided in Figure 1D. From each 3D reconstructed callus, several parameters were determined: bone volume over total volume (BV/TV, module *Volume Fraction*), average trabecular thickness (Tb.Th, module *Average Object Thickness*), average trabecular separation (Tb.Sp, module *Average Space Thickness*), trabecular number (Tb.Nm, module *Average Object Number per slice*), degree of anisotropy (DA, module *Degree of Anisotropy*), and Structural Model Index (SMI, module *Structure Model Index*), which defines the relative prevalence of rods and plates in the structure.

The connectivity of the woven trabecular networks (Conn.D) was calculated using the Euler-Poincaré formula for a 3D structure X [69]:

$$\chi(X) = \beta_0 - \beta_1 + \beta_2 \quad (1)$$

where χ is Euler-Poincaré number measured using the software Avizo (module *Euler Number 3D*), β_0 is the number of objects, β_1 is the connectivity, and β_2 is the number of enclosed pores. Following the well-established procedure for cancellous bone [69], it was assumed trabeculae fully interconnected with no isolated solids ($\beta_0 = 1$) and no marrow cavities within the bone ($\beta_2 = 0$). Note that the microporosities within the trabeculae will not be considered further as they are out of the analysis scale. Equation 1 may thus be reformulated as:

$$\beta_1 = 1 - \chi(X) \quad (2)$$

Control trabecular and cortical bone samples were also measured and analyzed using micro-CT. However, in the cortical sample, BV/TV was the only parameter calculated due to the absence of trabecular structures in this tissue.

2.3. Material analysis using Raman Spectroscopy

For the spectroscopy and nanoindentation tests, six rectangular regions of interest (800 x 800 μm) were selected in both woven and cortical tissues from each of the embedded and polished bone callus samples. Figure 1E shows an example of a composition of images taken with the microscope to select these areas of interest, highlighting examples of cortical and woven tissue. As indicated in Figure 1F, one area was always located in the proximal cortical fragment as a control reference. The other five zones were positioned to cover the proximal-distal (A-B-C) and medial-distal (B-D-E) directions.

Raman Spectroscopy analysis was performed using a LabRAM Horiba Jobin Yvon (HORIBA, Kyoto, Japan) confocal Raman microscope. Spectra were collected with a 785 nm red laser at 100x magnification, with a 5-second integration time and 20 accumulations. The spectral range was from 200 to 1800 cm^{-1} . The microscope was calibrated against a silicon standard prior to imaging each sample. Figure 1G presents examples of raw spectra taken by the Raman microscope, showing bone (green) and background fluorescence mainly from the embedding resin (blue). Then, background fluorescence removal and a baseline correction were applied to each individual spectrum using a cubic spline interpolation. Eight point-spectra were taken at different locations within each selected zone, resulting in a total of 48 spectra per bone callus sample. All spectra were taken in areas within the trabecula, thus avoiding porous points. Figure 1H provides an overview of the differences between corrected spectra from the cortical region and those from a woven bone area. The bands to analyze bone mineral phase are the phosphate band at 959 cm^{-1} ($\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}$), 422 cm^{-1} ($\nu_2\text{PO}_4^{3-}$) and the carbonate band at 1070 cm^{-1} [70,71]. The full-width half-height (FWHM) of the $\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}$ band is also interesting due to its inversely proportionality to mineral crystallite length and, therefore, is an indirect measure of mineral crystallinity. The most widely used bands to measure the matrix content are Proline at 853 cm^{-1} , Hydroxyproline at 872 cm^{-1} , Amide III at 1250 cm^{-1} , and Tyrosine at 1607 cm^{-1} [70,71]. The spectra were processed in MATLAB (R2022a, MathWorks, Natick, Massachusetts, US) to calculate intensity peaks (I), areas under the peaks (A), and broadness as full width at half maximum (FWHM). The parameters and ratios calculated are detailed in Table 1, indicating if they are related to the mineral or organic phase.

Table 1. Raman parameters in cortical and woven bone tissues calculated for each Raman spectra. I: maximum peak intensity, A: area under the peaks, FWHM: full width at half maximum. the subscript indicates the Raman shift position (cm^{-1}).

Raman parameter	Tissue phase	Ratio
Crystallinity	Mineral	$\frac{1}{FWHM_{959}}$
Carbonate-to-phosphate	Mineral	$\frac{I_{1070}}{I_{959}}$
$\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}$ /Proline mineral-to-matrix	Mineral/Organic	$\frac{I_{853}}{I_{959}}$
$\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}$ /Tyrosine mineral-to-matrix	Mineral/Organic	$\frac{I_{1607}}{I_{422}}$
$\nu_2\text{PO}_4^{3-}$ /Amide III mineral-to-matrix	Mineral/Organic	$\frac{A_{1250}}{A_{1070}}$
Carbonate-to-matrix	Mineral/Organic	$\frac{A_{1620-1700}}{I_{872}}$
Hydroxyproline-to-proline	Organic	$\frac{I_{853}}{I_{1620-1700}}$
Amide I-to-Amide III	Organic	$\frac{I_{1620-1700}}{I_{1250}}$

2.4. Mechanical properties using nanoindentation

The elastic modulus of the tissue was determined by nanoindentation tests on the same region of interest described in section 2.3. Nanoindentation was performed using a Nanotest indenter (Nanotest, Micro Materials Ltd. Wrexham, UK) equipped with a Berkovich diamond indenter. In each area, 16 x 16 indentations were made, spaced 50 μm apart in both directions, corresponding to the minimum trabecula thickness of naïve woven bone tissue [72]. Thus, a total of 256 indentations were performed per area, covering the entire region of interest. Figure 1I presents the load function applied to each indentation point. The load was increased at a rate of 0.5 mN/s to a maximum of 5 mN. Once the maximum load was reached in approximately 10 s, it was held constant for 40 s. The unloading was performed at the same rate. Examples of indentation curves in cortical (green) and woven bone tissues (black) are shown in Figure 1J. Note that the indentation depth, or the indenter's displacement, is a variable parameter that depends on the hardness of the tissue, being lower in cortical bone (see Figure 1J). The Oliver and Pharr method was used to calculate the elastic modulus (E) from the load-depth data [73]. Figures 1K and L, shows examples of nanoindentation maps measured on the region of interest marked in Figure 1E. The average elastic modulus per zone and its standard deviation were calculated by eliminating from the calculation those areas of porosity identified by microscope images or with elastic modulus less than 2 GPa.

2.5. Chemical analysis of the tissue

The second slice was employed for ash analysis and elemental analysis. The samples were initially ground with a sterilized pestle and mortar. They were then immediately dried in a BINDER VD 23 vacuum drying chamber (BINDER GmbH, Tuttlingen, Germany) using heating cycles at $105 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for one hour each, measuring the samples' weight at the end of each cycle until it stabilized. The resulting weight combines that corresponding to the mineral and organic phases ($m_m + m_o$) of the woven bone tissue after removing water. To obtain the ash fraction, the samples were ashed in a Nabertherm Muffle Furnace (Nabertherm GmbH, Lilienthal Germany) following the protocol provided by Martínez-Reina et al. [6]: (1) the temperature was initially increased from room temperature to 250°C over 30 minutes, and held at this temperature for 1 hour; (2) the temperature was gradually increased to 650°C over 30 minutes, and held for 2 hours; (3) the sample was then taken out of furnace and weighed; (4) the sample was reintroduced into the furnace at 650°C and maintained at this temperature for 30 minutes. Steps 3 and 4 were repeated until a constant weight was achieved. This process allowed removing the organic material. Therefore, the weight obtained at the end of the protocol corresponds to the mineral phase exclusively (m_m). The ash fraction α was finally calculated using Equation 3.

$$\alpha = \frac{m_m}{m_m + m_o} \quad (3)$$

An elemental analysis was also performed on the ashed samples to measure the calcium (Ca) mass percentage and trace element substitutions, mainly stable isotopes of carbon with oxygen in the carbonate (CO_3^{2-}) and hydrogen phosphate (HPO_4^{2-}) [6,74]. Hence, the mass percentages of

carbon (C) and phosphorus (P) were evaluated as an indirect measure of these impurities. Other possible calcium substitutes measured in the current study were sodium (Na), potassium (K) and other alkaline earth elements similar to calcium, including magnesium (Mg) or strontium (Sr) [74,75].

The elemental analysis of the carbon content was conducted using a TruSpec Micro analyzer (LECO Corporation, Michigan, US). The calcium and phosphorus contents were measured with an inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer SpectroBLUE (Spectro Analytical Instruments, Kleve, Germany) after the samples were dissolved in hydrochloric acid.

2.6. Definition of power laws for woven bone

The *ex vivo* experiments described in the previous sections will elucidate the evolution of the mechanical and chemical properties of woven bone during healing at the tissue scale, as well as the structural changes at the apparent level towards a cortical microarchitecture. In the literature, ash fraction or calcium content have been shown to be effective predictors of cancellous and cortical bone's mechanical properties [19,26,76]. Therefore, these parameters were used to define single-parameter power laws that predict the woven bone elastic modulus over the regeneration time, following Equation 4:

$$E = a \cdot x^b \quad (4)$$

where E is the elastic modulus, a and b are empirical constants derived from experimental data, and the variable x represents the predictor parameter. Specifically, empirical constants were fitted using the mean elastic modulus per sample measured by nanoindentation, evaluating the following experimental parameters as predictors: ash fraction ($x = \alpha$), calcium content ($x = Ca$) and phosphorus contents ($x = P$) measured by chemical analysis, and Raman ratios, $\nu_2\text{PO}_4^{3-}/\text{Amide III}$ mineral-to-matrix ($x = A_{422}/A_{1250}$) and $\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}/\text{Tyrosine}$ mineral-to-matrix ($x = I_{959}/I_{1607}$). Note that the $\nu_2\text{PO}_4^{3-}/\text{Amide III}$ ratio has been extensively shown to be proportional to calcium content, as measured by quantitative backscattered electron microscopy [71,77]. The phosphate $\nu_1\text{PO}_4^{3-}$, as a ratio indicative of organic matrix content, is also widely accepted as a measure of mineral content.

Given that the experimental data used to fit the empirical coefficients were measured at the micro-scale, the previous models predict the elastic modulus at the tissue scale. Consequently, a two-parameter power law function was also proposed to differentiate the influence of bone volume (BV/TV) and ash fraction (α) on an apparent macro-scale elastic modulus, as has been previously applied in cortical bone studies [19,76]:

$$E^* = a \cdot \alpha^b \cdot (BV/TV)^c \quad (5)$$

To adjust the coefficients of this second model, the volume fraction (BV/TV) measured by micro-CT were employed. Moreover, the apparent elastic modulus was taken by the model provided by Blázquez-Carmona et al. [1], which is based on experimental gait force data measured *in vivo* through instrumented external fixators and a load platform during gait tests on the same animals whose bone calluses were used in this work (R-square = 0.933, p-value < 0.001):

$$E^* = 3.76 \cdot e^{0.048 \cdot t} \quad (6)$$

where t is the day after surgery, and E^* is the apparent elastic modulus in MPa. Evaluating the time-points analyzed in this study, the apparent elastic modulus ranges between 0.01-8.53 GPa. The determination coefficients, R-square and p-values, were also calculated for all power laws defined above.

3. Results

3.1. Evolution of the woven bone microarchitecture

Figure 2 shows the evolution of the structural parameters measured in 3D reconstructed woven bone calluses from the micro-tomographic images. The BV/TV raised during the mineralization

process, as reported in Figure 2A. The calluses were partially mineralized shortly after the surgery, comprising 44.59% of the total callus volume after 18 days. Bone volume increased slightly over time, reaching 68.89% after 161 days. Throughout the analyzed period, the calluses had a volumetric fraction above that of the spongy bone in the proximal epiphysis (35.5%, red line) but below the surrounding cortical tissue (98.65%, green line). The size of the trabeculae increased significantly during the regeneration period from approximately 0.11 mm, similar to that of trabecular bone, to 0.29 mm, as shown in Figure 2B. In contrast, Figure 2C indicates that trabecular separation did not show a specific evolution, consistently remaining below the separation in the proximal cancellous bone. Both the trabecular number Tb.Nm (Figure 2D) and the connectivity Conn.D (Figure 2E) exhibited a similar pattern. A high number of trabecular structural structures with high connectivity were observed shortly after surgery. However, as trabeculae increased in size, these parameters decreased rapidly and stabilized at similar values to trabecular bone values. The degree of anisotropy (DA) remained constant between 0.45-0.51 (Figure 2F). Thus, similar to trabecular bone, although the structures showed a certain preferred orientation during trabecular formation, they were neither perfectly isotropic (DA=0) nor completely anisotropic (DA=1). Finally, Figure 2G shows a negative increase in the structural model index (SMI), indicating an increase in the concavity of the trabecular surfaces.

Figure 2. Evolution of the woven bone's microarchitecture measured from micro-tomographic images: (A) volume fraction; (B) trabecular thickness; (C) trabecular separation; (D) trabecular number; (E) connectivity density; (F) degree of anisotropy; (G) structural model index. Cortical and trabecular data is provided as a reference in green and red lines, respectively.

3.2. Elastic modulus of the bone callus

The average and standard deviation of the elastic modulus in each analyzed area, including the cortical region, are shown in Figure 3A. Additionally, nanoindentation maps of the analyzed zones, along with their corresponding microscopic reference images, are provided in Figure A1. Overall, no significant differences were found between the areas in any analyzed direction of the callus, either the proximal-distal direction (A-B-C) or the medial-lateral direction (B-D-E). In all samples, the elastic modulus of cortical tissue is double or triple that of woven bone. Figure 3B provides the temporal evolution of the elastic modulus of the bone callus, analyzing all regions of interest globally. Initially, the elastic modulus ranged from 3.07 to 6.32 GPa in the first weeks after surgery, and it increased slightly to 9.25 GPa after six months. During the analyzed period, the mechanical properties of woven bone remained significantly lower than those of cortical bone, whose elastic modulus was 16.44 ± 2.79 GPa.

Figure 3. Evolution of micro-scale the woven bone's elastic modulus measured by nanoindentation and chemical structure measured by Raman Spectroscopy. Mechanical properties: (A) elastic modulus by callus zones in each of the samples analyzed; (B) average elastic modulus of all the indentations made in all analyzed areas of the sample. Chemical structure: (C) Cristallinity; (D) Carbonate-to-phosphate; (E) Proline mineral-to-matrix; (F) Tyrosine mineral-to-matrix (G) Amide III mineral-to-matrix; (H) Carbonate-to-matrix; (I) Hydroxyproline-to-proline; (J) Amide I-to-Amide III. Data from cortical bone (mean and standard deviation) is provided in green.

3.3. Chemical composition of the woven bone

In this study, the chemical structures of woven and cortical bones were analyzed on both micro- and macro-scales. On the micro-scale, Figure 3 shows the evolution of the Raman parameters detailed in Table 1, calculated for each woven bone. The data is provided as the average ratios of all zones and all spectra taken from each. Figure A2 in Appendix A differentiates the results by areas of each sample. In both figures, the ratios calculated for the reference cortical tissue are shown in green. As shown in Figure 3C, the naïve woven bone tissue exhibited a degree of crystallinity comparable to that of cortical tissue from few days after surgery, without appreciable evolution over time. During regeneration, the carbonate-to-phosphate ratio was also similar to that of cortical bone, without significant differences in their standard deviation (Figure 3D). Figures 3E, F, and G cover the mineral amount of Phosphate v1 and v2 with respect to the organic components of the matrix: Proline, Tyrosine, and Amide III, respectively. Although no significant changes were observed when normalizing by Proline compared to the cortical tissue, the ratios against the other organic phases began significantly lower in woven bone compared to mature bone tissue, tending to approach cortical values during the regeneration phase. According to Figure 3H, the carbonate content of the newly formed bone tissue also increased relative to the organic phase until reaching cortical values. No trend was found in the Hydroxyproline-to-Proline (Figure 3I) and Amide I-to-Amide III (Figure 3J) ratios, but their standard deviations were significantly lower than those observed in woven bone.

Regarding the macro-scale chemical composition, Figure 4A shows the evolution of the ash fraction over the regeneration time. The mass fraction of the mineral component versus the organic component of the tissue increased significantly as the collagen template mineralized over time.

Consequently, the ash fraction increased progressively from 0.15-0.29 in the less mature calluses to 0.57 in the most ossified ones. This more consolidated callus reached an ash fraction similar to that of cortical tissue, $0.66 \pm 0.01\%$.

Figure 4. Evolution of the macro-scale woven bone's chemical composition measured with micro-analysis: (A) ash fraction; (B) carbon percentage; (C) calcium percentage; (D) potassium percentage; (E) magnesium percentage; (F) sodium percentage; (G) phosphorus percentage; (H) strontium percentage. Cortical data (mean and standard deviation) is provided as a reference in green lines.

The micro-elemental determinations of the chemical components specified in section 2.5 are also provided in Figures 4B-H. The carbon content (C%) slightly increased from 0.20 to 0.65%. However, the percentage of this element in all samples, including their cortical areas, remained relatively low ($< 1\%$). Figure 4C shows that calcium (Ca%) was the predominant element in all samples, with percentages ranging from 35.71 to 47.96%. Note that the calcium content in a cortical bone sample was estimated at $47.25 \pm 1.38\%$. Although a slight increase is seen throughout the regeneration phase, some of the least mature samples already showed calcium levels similar to cortical levels. Potassium (K%, Figure 4D), magnesium (Mg%, Figure 4E), and sodium (Na%, Figure 4F) followed a similar trend. All of these impurities began with percentage contents (0.48-0.71% for K; 0.57-0.89% for Mg; 1.80-2.71% for Na) above the cortical values of $0.08 \pm 0.01\%$, $0.45 \pm 0.04\%$, and $1.04 \pm 0.01\%$, respectively. However, all of them normalized over the period analyzed. As shown in Figure 4G, phosphorus (P%) was the second most abundant element, maintaining a relatively constant percentage between 20.03 and 24.16%, similar to that of cortical bone ($23.74 \pm 0.55\%$). Finally, the percentage of strontium (Sr%) was not significant in any sample, remaining around 0.02% in all cases (see Figure 4H).

3.4. Power laws: influence of structural and chemical properties of the elastic modulus

Table 2 presents the different power laws, the value of the empirical constants after adjustment with the experimental data, as well as the goodness-of-fit parameters: the R-square (R^2) and the p-value (P). Additionally, Figure 5 graphically represents these best-fit power law models of the tissue and apparent elastic modulus as functions of the predictor parameters, plotted against the experimental data. All single-parameter adjustments demonstrated high predictive strength of the tissue elastic modulus, with all R^2 values exceeding 0.5 and most of p-values below 0.05. The highest degrees of significance were observed in correlation based on Raman parameters. The largest resulting predictor exponent values were found in the Calcium content measured by chemical analysis ($b= 2.86$) and by Raman spectroscopy (Amide III mineral-to-matrix, $b= 2.64$).

Table 2. Definition of the power laws of the tissue and apparent elastic modulus (E in GPa) based of different structural and chemical measured parameters, fitting constants, and goodness-of-fit parameters, R-square (R^2) and p-value (P). Note that Cancium (Ca) and Phosphorus (P) in the power laws are expressed on a per unit basis.

Parameter	Power law	Constants			R^2	P
		a	b	c		
Ash fraction	$E = a \cdot \alpha^b$	20.84	1.26	-	0.55	0.091
Calcium	$E = a \cdot Ca^b$	71.56	2.86	-	0.72	0.031
Phosphorus	$E = a \cdot P^b$	349.85	2.62	-	0.56	0.104
Ash and volume fraction	$E^* = a \cdot \alpha^b \cdot BV/TV^c$	2.74e3	3.88	9.98	0.88	0.005
Amide III mineral-to-matrix	$E = a \cdot (A_{422}/A_{1250})^b$	2.79	2.64	-	0.83	0.011
Tyrosine mineral-to-matrix	$E = a \cdot (I_{1607}/I_{853})^b$	0.12	1.89	-	0.90	0.003

* Apparent elastic modulus measured *in vivo* by Blázquez-Carmona et al. [1].

The two-parameter power law model based on the ash fraction and bone volume fraction measured in the current study, alongside the macro-scale apparent elastic modulus provided by Blázquez-Carmona et al. [1] (Figure 5D), was also found to be highly significant ($R^2 = 0.88$ and $P = 0.005$). Furthermore, the best-fit volume fraction exponent value was nearly 3-fold the ash fraction exponent value, at 9.98 versus 3.88.

Figure 5. Correlations of the power laws defined in Table 2 to predict the tissue or apparent elastic modulus from the following structural and chemical parameters measured *ex vivo*: (A) ash fraction from chemical analysis; (B) calcium content from chemical analysis; (C) phosphorus content from chemical analysis; (D) ash fraction from chemical analysis and volume fraction from micro-CT; (E) $v_2PO_4^{3-}$ /Amide III mineral-to-matrix from Raman Spectroscopy, undertood as the calcium content; (F) $v_1PO_4^{3-}$ /Tyrosine mineral-to-matrix from Raman Spectroscopy.

4. Discussion

Quantifying the structural, chemical, and mechanical properties of the woven bone is crucial for understanding the mechanobiology behind bone regeneration and assessing the effectiveness of ortopaedic approaches for healing critical-sized bone defects. Equally important is the parallel development of numerical models that optimize key engineering parameters to control this biological process and prevent non-unions. There is a notable lack of micromechanical models of woven bone in the literature based on *ex vivo* experimental data that consider changes in tissue properties at different regeneration phases. The multiscale research presented here analyzed the evolution of the trabeculae organization in this immature tissue through micro-CT, its elastic modulus using nanoindentation, its mineral quality via Raman spectroscopy, and its chemical composition with

ash analysis. From these experiments, power laws based on physical measurements were defined for the first time, relating the elastic modulus of the woven bone with its porosity and mineralization state. In addition, the data and power laws provided in this study are highly extrapolated to human bone tissues due to the ovine nature of the samples. Newman et al. [78] reported high similarities in bone composition between mature sheep and humans. Similarly, de Boer et al. [79] found comparable metabolic and bone remodeling rates using dual energy X-ray absorptiometry. The results obtained in this study also try to address some open questions in the field: Why is the stiffness of woven bone lower than that of cortical bone? Is it solely due to the mineral content, or is it influenced by the structural factors as well?; Do structural and mineral changes equally contribute to the bulk mechanical properties of woven bone? Are Raman spectra valid inputs for defining power laws?

The mechanical properties of the woven bone tissue exhibited a slight increase over the analyzed regeneration period, as indicated by the elastic modulus measured by nanoindentation, which ranged from 3.07 to 9.25 GPa (see Figures 3A and B and Figure A1). However, the stiffness levels characteristic of cortical tissue, approximately 16.44 ± 2.79 GPa, were not reached even after 161 days post-surgery. Previous studies by Manjubala et al. [56], Leong and Morgan [55], and Mora-Macías et al. [57] also used nanoindentation to measure the elastic modulus of bone calluses formed during other regeneration processes. Manjubala et al. [56] reported values in the range of 2–13 GPa over the first 9 week of a fracture healing experiment in an ovine tibia. Thus, the woven tissue associated to this regeneration process reached higher stiffness at a greater speed, likely due to the smaller size of the bone gap in fracture healing, approximately 3 mm in this study. Similarly, Leong and Morgan [55] conducted indentation tests on rodent fracture healing calluses, reporting an elastic modulus ranging from 0.03 to 1.01 GPa at day 35 after fracture. These results are significantly lower than those observed in the current study, possibly due to the different animal model used and the earlier healing stage analyzed. In another study, Mora-Macías et al. [57] also measured elastic modulus values ranging from 7 to 14 GPa in bone transport calluses of the ovine metatarsus with the same critical size of 15 mm. Specifically, they reported an elastic modulus of 11 GPa after 161 days in bone transport [57], closely matching the 9.25 ± 2.93 GPa measured in this study during bone lengthening at the same time-point. The possible lower degree of mechanical maturation in the bone lengthening callus could be explained by a lower mechanical stimulation associated to the less mobility and bearing capacity of the specimens after the indirect elongation of the surrounding soft tissues [67]. These findings reflect a slower recovery of the mechanical properties of the woven bone at the tissue scale throughout its remodeling phase. It is important to highlight that nanoindentation tests specifically excluded the influence of inter-trabecular macroporosities on the average data provided. Consequently, the observed lower stiffness can only be attributed to the presence of microporosities or other microstructural features at smaller length scales, or to differences in the chemical composition and organization of the deposited mineral phase, as discussed later.

The mineral content in woven bone has been previously examined in the literature. Manjubala et al. [56] measured calcium content directly from backscattered electron microscopic images (2D mineral content), showing inhomogeneity in the callus mineralization with a maximum Ca content of 20% of Ca that saturates at week 9 after surgery. In cortical bone, Turunen et al. [8] investigated the temporal evolution of mineral content during aging with Infrared and Raman spectroscopy. They found that while mineralization increases over time, hydroxyapatite crystals mature more slowly. Ahmed et al. [33] reported an increase in the mineral-to-matrix and crystallinity ratios during the first 14 days of healing in calvarial defects through Raman Spectroscopy. In our study, bone mineralization during healing was quantified at the microscopic scale using several Raman parameters, including mineral-to-matrix and carbonate-to-matrix ratios. Figure 3 demonstrates the positive correlation between the Tyrosine and Amide III mineral-to-matrix and healing time, reaching values comparable to those of cortical bone at day 161. These measurements provide a quantitative assessment of the extent of bone mineralization, directly related to ash weight [80]. Crystallinity, which is a measure of the crystal size development [8], remained nearly constant during the consolidation phase, with values similar to those of the cortical bone (Figure 3C). Given that osteoid is deposited by osteoblasts at different locations and timing within

the callus, this finding suggests that the maximum crystal size is obtained in an early stage of regeneration. Despite the increase in the carbonate-to-matrix ratio observed in Figure 3H, the carbonate-to-phosphate ratio (Figure 3D) showed no significant trend during the consolidation phase, maintaining values akin to those of cortical bone. Similar results were reported in calvarian healing [33]. This ratio represents type-B carbonate substitution into hydroxyapatite, a process not fully understood but associated with increased solubility and decreased mechanical performance of the tissue [81]. Literature suggests this substitution is more related to aging, as carbonate peak areas and intensities increase with age [11,82]. Regarding the hydroxyproline-to-proline ratio, the literature proved that it negatively correlates with the maturation of the tissue [83]. However, it keeps constant in woven bone and within the standard deviation range of cortical bone according to Figure 3G. As shown in Figure 3J, a similar trend was observed for the Amide I-to-Amide III ratio, which remained approximately constant above 1. It follows a very similar trend to crystallinity, as both processes are closely correlated with the bone formation. Initially, naïve collagen fibers are created followed by an enzymatically crosslinking [84]. These fibers then mineralized and served as scaffolds for the nucleation and growth of the additional mineral crystals [80]. A high Amide I-to-Amide III ratio indicates a predominance of functional and mature collagen crosslinks, whereas a predominance of Amide III suggests high activity of nonfunctional precursor collagen with reducible crosslinks [70,71,85]. Thus, woven bone exhibits an increase in procollagen molecules and immature crosslinks during the analyzed regeneration phase.

Figure 4 also reported the chemical analysis performed by ash analysis and elemental study. The ash fraction, phosphorous and calcium content increased nonlinearly with healing time with a plateau nearly the cortical reference values. Phosphorous and calcium contents are also in line with the infrared and X-ray analysis on natural hydroxyapatite [86]. Numerous substituents were reported in hydroxyapatite crystals in the literature, including carbon, potassium, magnesium, sodium, or strontium. For potassium and sodium, the decrease with time was quantified (Figures 4D and F) [74,75,87]. However, none of the above substituents seems to play a key role during the bone regeneration process.

Regarding the structural features of the woven bone at the trabecular scale, as measured by micro-CT and illustrated in Figure 2, the BV/TV increased up to 0.69. This increase is primarily due to an increase in the trabecular thickness (Tb.Th) as the different mineralization fronts advance. Previous studies have already examined bone volume fraction using different techniques and length scales. For instance, Blázquez-Carmona et al. [1] and Mora-Macías et al. [2] measured the bone volume fraction from CT macroscopic images in bone lengthening and bone transport, respectively. In these studies, the volume fraction ranged from 88.18–93.97% in bone lengthening and 87.55–100% in bone transport at days 121–161 after surgery. The lower values in our study are more consistent with estimates provided by Mora-Macías et al. [2], which used direct segmentation of 2D micrographs based on x-ray grey-scale images. Thus, the porosity at the trabecular scale appears to significantly impact the estimation of the bulk volume fraction. This structural feature likely contributes to the differences found in the same period of time between the micro-scale elastic modulus measured in this study (3.07–9.25 GPa), and the lower apparent elastic modulus measured *in vivo* by Blázquez-Carmona et al. [1] (0.01–8.53 GPa), input in a later discussed power law. Compared to the trabecular tissue, woven bone only exhibits BV/TV levels similar to those observed in this study or those reported in femoral bone by Mittra et al. [88] or Teo et al. [89] at the early stages of regeneration. The other three-dimensional microarchitectural parameters of woven bone provided in Figure 2 could not be directly compared to other regenerating tissues due to the lack of reported data in the literature, to our knowledge. Therefore, comparisons are limited to cancellous bone tissue data from this study or literature sources [82,88,89]. The aforementioned increase in Tb.Th above cancellous values occurs alongside a progressive reduction of the number (Tb.Nm) and interconnectivity (Conn.D) of woven trabeculae, more similar to that of healthy metatarsal trabecular tissue, 3 cm^{-1} and 12.79, respectively. These reference trabecular values are slightly higher than those of healthy ovine or human femoral trabecular tissue reported in the literature [82,88,89], probably due to physiological differences between bones. The stabilization of the woven trabecular separation around 0.13–0.17 mm (Figures 2C) contrasts with the constant increase in Tb.Th, which can only be explained by the remodeling of already mineralized tissue

in the medullary cavity or the outer interzones of the callus farthest from the original cortical bone. The degree of anisotropy (DA) remained similar to that of trabecular tissue in the same bone (0.52, Figures 2F) or to values reported in human femoral bone by Turunen et al. [82], Finally, SMI evolved negatively from around 0, typical for trabecular bone [82,88], indicating a transition from a rod-and-plate structure typical of trabecular bone to a denser structure characterized by void spaces [90]. These results highlight the dynamic evolution of woven bone microstructure, from numerous disorganized thin trabeculae at the beginning of the consolidation phase to a structure with fewer but thicker and better-interconnected trabeculae.

The previous experimental data facilitated the definition of the power laws presented in Table 2, which serve as valuable tools for predicting the elastic modulus of woven bone in future *in silico* models at both macro- and micro-scales. The varied laws allow for the assignment of woven bone tissue mechanical properties based on different experimental results, not necessarily mechanical testing. Except for the current study, woven bone correlations have never been established using mechanical, structural and chemical parameters measured directly from *ex vivo* samples. The exponents of these expressions (b and c fitting constants in Table 2) provide insights into the degree of influence of chemical composition (measured at the macro- scale by ash and elemental analyses and at the micro-scale by Raman spectroscopy) and microstructural morphology on the mechanical properties of the woven bone at both macro- and micro-scale. For instance, the ash fraction appears to have a lower relative influence on the elastic modulus measured by nanoindentation ($b = 1.26$) over a broad range of ash fraction values compared to the calcium or phosphorous contents ($b = 2.62 - 2.86$). This exponent is also slightly lower than those in equivalent power laws reported in the literature [13,19,76]. The differences can be attributed to the use of compact and cancellous bone tissues from different mammalian species, the range of ash fractions analyzed, and the different loading conditions in the mechanical characterization. The degree of significance of all correlation (R^2 in range of 0.55-0.90 and most of p-values below 0.05) is consistent with previous works [13,19,76]. However, Raman parameters, Amide III mineral-to-matrix and Tyrosine mineral-to-matrix, were found to correlate more significantly with elastic modulus than ash, calcium or phosphorus fractions (Figures 3A, B, C, E and J, and Table 2). We hypothesize it could also be due to significant chemical heterogeneity in the tissue. Note that the Raman spectra were taken in the same areas of woven bone as those measured by nanoindentation. We also define a two-parameter function to explain more of the variance in the bulk mechanical properties of the woven bone than single-parameter functions based solely on chemical factors. Thus, the combination of ash fraction with the evolution of the BV/TV provides a significant correlation with the apparent elastic modulus (Figure 3D and Table 2), representing mechanical behavior at a macro-scale. In this case, the substantial difference between the ash fraction ($b = 3.88$) and the BV/TV exponent values ($c = 9.98$) indicates a greater influence of the bone volume evolution over the total callus volume, encompassing both mineralized and non-mineralized phases, on the bone callus' apparent mechanical properties during healing, compared to the influence of the ash fraction. This finding contrasts with previous reports on cortical and trabecular tissue in the literature, where ash fraction seems to have a significant greater influence on bone strength and modulus [76], possibly due to the less structural remodeling and time depending nature of healthy bone tissues.

There are several limitations associated with the methodology employed in this study. Firstly, it is expected that the mechanical, structural and chemical parameters analyzed *ex vivo* are not significantly influenced by differences in bone maturity of sheep during the regeneration period *in vivo* since the longest experiment (161 days) represents only around 4% of the animal life cycle. Secondly, the methods used for the indentation test [73] assume linear elastic behavior in the tissue, despite the possibility that the woven bone could exhibit viscoelastic behavior in some callus interzones, particularly during early stage of mineralization. However, the mechanical characterization performed in this study is focused on the mineralized phase, where the influence of the viscoelastic behavior should not be significant compared to a soft tissue [67]. Additionally, the use of different specimens for each time-point introduces an inevitable source of variation in the measurements. Despite this, the results appear to follow logical trends, and the power laws derived are significant. Finally, a higher number of animals would have enhance the statistical

significance of the conclusions of this study. As previously mentioned, the authors prioritized the use of an ovine animal model, whose results are crucial for construction of more realistic micromechanical models and whose conclusions can be readily extrapolated to human clinical cases.

In conclusion, this work contributes to the development of novel micromechanical models applicable to numerical simulations of bone regeneration processes. It also enhances the understanding of the relationship between chemical composition, structural morphology, and the mechanical properties of woven bone at different length scales by combining multiple *ex vivo* techniques: micro-CT, nanoindentation, Raman spectroscopy, and chemical and elemental analysis. Addressing the questions posed at the beginning of the discussion, woven bone exhibited a significant increase in bone volume, primarily controlled by the thickening and unification of trabeculae, alongside a simultaneous increase in apparent ash fraction, calcium, and phosphate content. The power law established for the bulk elastic modulus highlights a more significant influence of the evolving trabecular microarchitecture on the apparent mechanical behavior of the bone callus. At the tissue scale, the Raman mineral-to-matrix ratio increased over the analyzed regeneration period, reaching values and crystallinity levels comparable to those of cortical bone. However, the local elastic modulus did not increase sufficiently to reach cortical values, potentially due to the role of microporosities within the trabeculae. Power laws predicting the evolution of the woven bone elastic modulus at this scale demonstrated that Raman parameters correlate better with the elastic modulus than apparent mineral content measured through ash analysis and elemental studies. Therefore, we advocate for the combined use of Raman spectroscopy and nanoindentation in constructing future power laws for regenerating tissue, potentially strengthened by including a second parameter to account for structural features at the microscale.

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Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

BV/TV	Bone volume over total volume
Conn.D	Connectivity density
C	Carbon
Ca	Calcium
CT	Computed tomography
DA	Degree of anisotropy
E	Elastic modulus
FWHM	Full width at half maximum
K	Potassium
Mg	Magnesium
Na	Sodium
P	Phosphorus
PBS	Phosphate-buffered saline
SMI	Structural Model Index
Sr	Strontium
Tb.Nm	Trabecular number
Tb.Sp	Trabecular separation
Tb.Th	Trabecular thickness

Appendix A

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Figure A1. Nanindentation maps of all analyzed zones of the bone callus samples.

Figure A2. Evolution of the woven bone's chemical composition measured with micro-analysis in each analyzed zone of the bone calluses: (A) ash fraction; (B) carbon percentage; (C) calcium percentage; (D) potassium percentage; (E) magnesium percentage; (F) sodium percentage; (G) phosphorus percentage; (H) strontium percentage. Results of the cortical area of the callus (mean and standard deviation) is provided as a reference in green

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